

Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

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UNU MERIT- Maastricht Governance School

Moderator: Teoman Pamukçu

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, April 29, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/qULdGE9MFxgNDiaVA>

Moderation: Prof. Dr. Teoman Pamukçu

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 28 April 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 28 April 2022.

Abstract: Responsible and resilient design of technological change and innovation call for early stage engagement and experimentation with relevant stakeholders in each stage of a value chain, which extends to digitizing, financing to marketing actors, for sustainable, multiple value transitions of (energy) systems and transformation of societies. Policy interventions collapse into non-intervention if market and non-market returns on public funding do not involve explicit return on investment and impact targets towards expected socio-economic and socio-ecological outcomes. In this regard, measurement of the speed of transformation among varieties of capital (e.g. from financial capital to human capital; from social capital to natural capital, and back to financial capital) requires more real-time (e.g. complementarily to annual indicators) and contextual (e.g. I/O and process legitimacy of an intervention) measurement and indicators. This challenges traditional measures of socio-economic (e.g. employment effect) and ecological economics (e.g. resource efficiency) measures. Moving forward with novel social (e.g. work satisfaction) and ecological (e.g. occupational health in a livelihood) measures and indicators requires real-time, and contextual measurement, which benefit from both digital and social small data and big data, that help support not rendering the measurement efforts to non-measurement.

Speaker:

Asst. Prof. Dr. Serdar Türkeli conducts policy research at the United Nations University - Maastricht Economic and Social Research Institute on Innovation and Technology (UNU-MERIT United Nations University), Maastricht University. He applies quantitative and/or qualitative methods to critical political economy and policy issues related to governance of science, technology and innovation (STI), STI policies and their governance for sustainability, system transitions and societal transformations. He is currently, lead for comprehensive innovation for system transitions and climate change research team, co-lead of adaptation and sustainable transformations for UNU Climate Resilience Initiative, UNU-MERIT, UNU-EHS, UNU-CRIS; Lead in Resilience, Responsible and Sustainable Initiatives Observatory, MORSE Initiative, UM; Research Director, Climate Programme, 89 Netherlands (Studio Europa Maastricht Joint Initiative); Advisor, UNDP SDG AI Lab, (Joint initiative of UNDP Nature, Climate, and Energy Cluster, UNDP Finance Sector Hub, UNDP Istanbul International Center for Private Sector in Development (IICPSD), and UNV-IICPSD Digital

Transformation Partnership); and Member of the Steering Board, Eco-Innovation Society and featured expert in SDG 12 Responsible Production and Consumption by UNU SDG Explorer.

About SolarTwins-TEKPOL Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) – Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	Energy Security Challenges: Assessing Turkey's Role in Changing Regional Dynamics (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAK _{TR} : Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	Sara Banu AKKAŞ and Zelal ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective (in Turkish)

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SolarTwins has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 856619.